

BIG DATA EFFECT ON BASE OF THE PYRAMID SEGMENT

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Abstract

Big data refers to huge voluminous sets of data that requires advanced technologies to manage it. Today, the word has evolved to it also refers to predictive analytics, user behaviour analytics and other advanced analytic methods that churn value from data. Information and data is growing very rapidly because various devices are equipped with technology to capture data in a myriad of ways. By 2025, IDC predicts that there will be 163 zettabytes of data.

The base of the pyramid markets is the growing 4 billion populations who are living on less than \$ 2 a day. Management thinkers, Prahalad and Hart, in 1999, propounded their idea on how multinationals can help alleviate poverty and generate profits successfully by selling their products in these markets; many companies have been looking at strategies to serve the BOP segment in emerging markets. The attraction of the BOP segment has been a topic of research for close to two decades; however the concept of churning valued information from big data and its applicability to doing business better is prevalent only since 3-4 years. Any number of primary and secondary research studies can throw up information on predictive behaviour, cause effect relationships and so on but a prediction can be done more realistically when there is lot of concrete data to back the predictions. Big data serves exactly the same purpose.

Keywords: Analytics, big data, BOP, opportunity, strategies

1. Introduction

Big data has been a very relevant concept in today's business world. As a term it is going through a constant pace of evolution, earlier it was meant to denote large amounts of information, today big data even includes aspects which refer to predictive analytics, user behaviour analytics and other advanced analytic methods that churn value from data. So, it has gone through a sea change since the word was first coined where it was used to refer to just large sets of data.

The evolution of 'big data' - even before the digital age, computers and databases we have had information which was stored on paper in customer records, transaction records, archived files and so on. The computer age with spreadsheets, databases paved the way to store and access this volume of information in an easy manner which was quick and easy to store and retrieve. The term in its current use encompass three Vs - Volume, velocity and variety. Big data

basically works on the simple principal that the more information you have about something, the more reliably we can make predictions about something or gain insights into the future. Big data can be broken down by various data point classifications such as demographic, psychographic, behavioural and transactional data. Then by building models using this data and then simulating this data, new relationships emerge.

2. BOP

The bottom of the pyramid (BOP) was a term used as back as by president Roosevelt to refer to people at the very bottom of the economic pyramid with very frugal means and very low incomes. Over a period of time it was termed base of the pyramid to take away the negative connotation when we use the term 'bottom'. As propounded by C.K. Prahalad and Stuart L. Hart in 'The Fortune at the Bottom of the Pyramid' (2002) used the 4-tiered pyramid to represent the global distribution of wealth and the capacity to generate income. Right at the top of the world economic pyramid are 75 to 100 million affluent Tier I consumers from around the world. This is a cosmopolitan group composed of middle- and upper-income people in developed countries and the few rich elites from the developing world. In the middle of the pyramid, in Tiers 2 and 3, are poor customers in developed nations and the rising middle classes in developing countries, the targets of MNCs' past emerging-market strategies. They categorised 4 billion people in Tier 4 i.e at the bottom of the pyramid. Their annual per capita income based on purchasing power parity in U.S. dollars is less than \$1,500, the minimum considered necessary to sustain a decent life. For well over a billion people roughly one-sixth of humanity per capita income is less than \$1 per day.

As per World Bank projections, the population at the bottom of the pyramid could swell to more than 6 billion people over the next 40 years, this is due to the fact that the bulk of the world's population growth occurs there. Most Tier 4 people live in rural villages, or urban slums and shantytowns, and they usually do not hold legal title or deed to their assets (e.g., dwellings, farms, businesses).

3. The importance of big data for the base of the pyramid markets –the BOP markets in most cases are in informal settings within a larger informal economy. The most basic of the human needs for sustenance - food, clothing and shelter are not met. Certain BOP markets may be self sufficient but there are various gaps and even the basic needs are not getting fulfilled completely in their own subsystems. For instance, the consumer might be living in a makeshift thatched kuccha dwelling, even to repair this dwelling and live in it on a day to day basis he may need to procure plastic sheets, containers and so on. This may not be available in his subsystem and he will have to scout and buy it from a local vendor. Hence, a market is created.

Certain opportunities offered by big data for BOP market operators are –

1. JAM – The Jan Dhan account mobilisation initiative along with the UIDAI rollout of the Aadhar identity cards and the movement towards focus on mobile communication devices has been a major information and data garner for an emerging economy like India. As per statistics' more than 295 million accounts have been mobilised under then Jan Dhan scheme. This is a huge step when more than 70% of the Indian adult population is considered to be financially illiterate and banking has made little inroads to the BOP communities. This step

along with making Aadhar mandatory for many transactions has ensured that the large wide spread informal economy is brought under the organized economy purview over a period of time. Prior to the launch of Jan Dhan scheme more than 35% of Indian households did not have access to a bank account. This move will eventually move a large chunk of the population especially in the BOP segment from cash based transactions to digital transactions and this would give a major boost to the economic growth. In unorganized sectors and BOP segments there are major cash transactions, which are not accounted for, and to that extent the taxes are also evaded. To initiate any policy initiatives also data is not available for the government and agencies of the cash and financial habits of the BOP consumers, they have been largely ignored by developmental initiatives because they could not have been accounted for, this simple program and the continued thrust would provide adequate data for the government as well.

2. Health Care Initiatives – India, as we see today is demographically young with more than 65 per cent of the population below the age of 35 years and more than 50 per cent of the population below the age of 25 years. However, with time and the slowdown in the birth rate and decreasing life expectancy India will be faced with a major demand for healthcare services. Especially in the BOP segment there has been no healthcare programs and the needs of this sector is largely unknown. Since a major portion of the population in emerging economies are in the low income segment, their numbers are large and a lot can be gathered if proper information can be gathered across health centres and hospitals, with the digitization drive in India, e-health and m-health are raging trends that are being targeted by large and small health care providers.

3. Other digital Initiatives – With the digitization program of the government of India, many initiatives have taken off to incorporate more data availability thus ensuring that there is big data for future use in all sectors and which will aid in decision making and designing strategic policies. Some of these initiatives are the digitization of transactions at various points of sales of mobile sim cards, e-ticketing, financial services will provide lot of information that will be converted as big data. While it becomes mandatory to quote identification numbers for mobile sim cards it will help in getting an account of the width and breadth of the economy, interestingly today, in the BOP segments they may not have access to basic necessities' such as electricity or drinking water or sanitation but mobiles are available. This move of getting registered under the Aadhar (UIDAI) identity process and the requirement to quote the same would ensure seamless availability of information regarding each and every customer. The financial services sector has also seen a turnaround by making this segment come under the purview of the JanDhan scheme; the government has mandatorily ensured that all schemes and subsidies for the poor sections would directly be transferred to their accounts. This would further ensure obligatory mobilisation of accounts and rooting of transactions through these accounts. This would be a great step in getting the informal BOP sector to be accounted for and great amount of information for predictive analysis being available. Additionally, making quoting of unique identity numbers at POS (point of sales) and online sites of the road transport corporation, train ticketing centers would create a data base of travellers and their travel patterns. Finally, the internet of things (IOT) has enabled fast paced data collection points. Most devices throw up myriad variants of information on a large scheme of things from every sector of the economy. This data enabling mechanisms can be fruitfully collaborated with to create pools of big data and analytics.

4. Suggestions & Conclusion

Although this is an attempt to understand and analyse the facets of big data from the standpoint of the base of the pyramid markets, these initiatives are a starting point for getting detailed information on the much neglected BOP segment. Big data has a great impact to strengthen the BOP market mechanisms. Many multinationals and large corporations have failed miserably in certain strategies they have adopted in entering and serving these markets. These failures have been after considerable years of research and test marketing had been done which in itself turned up information. Information which is not backed by actual purchase data and on the ground reality will only continue to be information and the predictions based on these cannot be reliable enough for predicting future behaviour. Hence, this data churn termed big data when gathered for BOP consumers would make the efforts of multinationals, large corporations, government and aided agencies who have been serving these markets by providing various products and services would be highly beneficial. Even from the standpoint policy making and serving the most underserved segments of the BOP markets becomes easier. Within BOP segments there are certain mature markets and the major portion of largely the immature crude uninformed market. It would take a longer period of time to gather valuable data from all of these segments but a step in the positive direction is making strategic decision making easier.
